

Grounded Theory on the Winning Qualities of Student Athletes

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Abstract

Student-athletes acquire qualities like teamwork, time management, and leadership, contributing to their holistic development. Understanding athletes' performance histories, genes, environment, and other characteristics is critical for developing talent. The BPSU Swimming team has consistently excelled in swimming competitions, and this study aims to evaluate the key qualities that lead to the success of student-athletes and provide practical insights for their development. This study used a grounded theory approach to understand the qualities that make student-athletes successful. The study involved fourteen participants, including athletes, parents, coaches, a trainer, and officials, and data was collected through focus group discussions and interviews, following the principles of grounded theory methodology. The study identified several themes that describe the talent development experiences and influences of university swimming athletes. These themes include the role of genetics and physical characteristics, environmental opportunities and personal sacrifices, early successes in swimming, challenges faced by swimmers and coping mechanisms, as well as the role of family, coaches, teammates, and school in nurturing positive influences. These factors together contribute to the success and growth of the university's swimming athletes, highlighting the importance of investigating the combination of experiences and influences in studying talent development. The study also proposes a theory explaining how experiences and influences contribute to achieving swimming excellence and shaping the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

Keywords: Student-athletes, Winning Qualities, Sports, Talent Development

Introduction

Sports offers an avenue to explore their potential and strive for physical excellence, as highlighted by Martindale et al. (2014). Participating in sports is not only a significant decision but also a commitment that impacts a student's academic journey. It involves careful consideration of various factors, as it requires dedicated effort. According to MU Health Care (2023), engaging in sports demands a substantial amount of time and energy. Sports necessitate the development of memorization, repetitive practice, and learning abilities, skill sets directly applicable to academic performance. Moreover, the determination and goal-setting skills acquired through sports can be successfully transferred to the classroom environment. That being said, athletic success often necessitates the cultivation of certain personal qualities, such as diligent effort, self-discipline, unwavering perseverance, resolute determination, and unwavering focus. These attributes play a crucial role in enabling athletes to excel in their chosen disciplines.

According to Pinkerton et al. (2010), the pursuit of sporting activities encompasses more than mere physical exertion. Student-athletes acquire essential personal qualities, including teamwork, time management, mental health awareness, work ethic, leadership, and commitment. These attributes contribute to their holistic development as individuals. That being said, student-athletes must exhibit a unique blend of qualities that greatly impact their accomplishments, both on the field and in the classroom. As such, acquiring a comprehensive understanding of these winning attributes can provide educators, coaches, and parents with valuable insights to effectively support the holistic development of student-athletes.

In recent years, there has been a growing appreciation of the way sports are recognized and treasured in society. As a result, institutions have highlighted providing student-athletes with the essential provision to flourish in their athletic pursuits while also maintaining their academic responsibilities. According to Gomez et al. (2018), achieving excellence as an athlete requires significant time, commitment, and well-planned training. It is also crucial for student-athletes to find a balance between training and rest to adapt effectively. Amid a highly competitive environment, student-athletes face the challenge of managing these demands alongside their academic obligations.

Furthermore, Williams et al. (2020) state that psychological traits are now a crucial part of multifaceted models of athlete development. Early studies revealed that

young athletes who performed better than their peers had superior psychological capacities that enabled them to develop more. Throughout the past 20 years, psychological traits have been extensively studied and are important indicators of both development and adult success in addition to being consistently linked to youth players' present performance levels (Murr et al., 2018). Furthermore, a variety of significant psychological traits have been found through psychological research and linked to subjective coach, player, and scout perceptions and objective performance metrics (Williams et al., 2020).

Additionally, in the research conducted by Elferink-Gemser et al. (2012), it was emphasized that talent development programs have a specific objective of fostering players toward achieving a professional level of performance. When identifying, nurturing, and selecting young players, scouts, trainers, and coaches must acknowledge the existing level of their knowledge in their respective sports and the underlying performance characteristics, such as intermittent endurance capacity, as they are expected to improve over time. It is essential to recognize that this factor may have a significant impact on the aspirations of current young players who aim to reach the highest level of their sport in the next ten years. Given this, understanding athletes' performance histories, their genes (Turkheimer, 2000), their environment, and other physical and psychological characteristics are becoming increasingly recognized as critical components of developing a talent development strategy. Thus, it is critical to ascertain the athletes' thorough and practical preparation, family aid, expert coaching, adequate physical services, and psychological traits (Hamrouni et al. (2015). It is vital to explore the relationship between many crucial elements to acquire a thorough knowledge of swimmers' abilities throughout sports activities.

Furthermore, as per Simonton (2001), talent development in sports is a complex and constantly evolving process that involves the interaction of performance, psychosocial, and educational factors. This process encompasses multiple stages within the sport, including initiation, talent development, talent retention, mastery, perfection/elite performance, as well as educational milestones such as elementary school, high school, and college/university/vocational education. Furthermore, making well-informed decisions regarding pursuing an athletic career is crucial, as they have a direct impact on athletes' lives and their academic, sporting, familial, and peer support networks (Ryba et al., 2015). It is important to note that the literature on sports talent identification highlights the significance of key individuals and organizations in facilitating the holistic development of talented athletes. These

influential actors play a vital role in promoting athlete well-being, providing support during stressful situations across various areas of life (e.g., training intensity, competition demands, injuries, social life constraints, and transitions to higher levels of competition and academia). Thus, it is worth emphasizing that by adopting a comprehensive approach to talent development, athletes can optimize their potential while balancing their academic pursuits, personal relationships, and overall physical and mental well-being.

Over the past years, the Bataan Peninsula State University (BPSU) Swimming team consistently garnered more than 30 gold medals each year, which put them ranked number one in the SCUAA SUC III Olympics. Nonetheless, the overarching objective of the esteemed university is to cultivate the proficiency and prowess of our aspiring students, equipping them with the necessary skills to excel and emerge victorious across a diverse range of swimming competitions. That being said, the researcher arrived at this study and examined and evaluated the key qualities that lead to the success of student-athletes. By doing so, this study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the pivotal factors that contribute to their achievements in sports and academics. Through a systematic analysis of these qualities, this research aspires to offer practical and evidence-based insights for educational professionals, coaches, and parents in fostering the holistic development of student-athletes.

Methods

In this study, a grounded theory approach was employed to achieve the research objective of understanding and identifying the winning qualities of student-athletes. Grounded theory is a research method that aims to generate a substantive theory by thoroughly examining an empirical sociological and organizational inquiry (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The use of grounded theory is particularly valuable when investigating social phenomena that have not been extensively studied before. It is also well-suited for capturing the complex dynamics and behaviors within organizations (Locke, 2001).

Moreover, grounded theory generation is based on context-specific and process-oriented explanations of a social phenomenon. This is accomplished through the analysis of representative examples of data, allowing for a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The process of theory generation in grounded theory is inductive, meaning that data collection and analysis unfold together, allowing for the emergence of patterns and insights (Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

Through this iterative process, the researchers can uncover and articulate local understandings that would otherwise remain implicit and unexplained.

The aforementioned approach is appropriate to the study since grounded theory is a qualitative research methodology used to develop theories about phenomena in the social sciences. It involves gathering and analyzing data to construct theories that are "grounded" in the data itself, rather than starting with preconceived hypotheses. The process typically involves open coding, axial coding, and selective coding to identify patterns and categories in the data, ultimately leading to the development of a substantive theory. Grounded theory is often used in sociology, psychology, nursing, and other social science fields to explore and understand complex social phenomena.

In addition, there were fourteen (14) participants in the study, four (4) swimming athletes, four (4) parents of the athletes, three (3) coaches, one (1) trainer, and two (2) swimming officials. This sample size allows for in-depth exploration and analysis of the participants' experiences and perspectives, which is fundamental to grounded theory methodology.

Moreover, the qualitative method explored the experiences of participants through focus group discussion. In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted by the researcher through telephone with all participants of the study. Meanwhile, interviews consist of collecting data by asking questions. A structured discussion to stimulate conversation around a specific topic is led by a facilitator who poses questions and the participants give their thoughts and opinions (Abawi, 2013). Additionally, these in-depth interviews were analyzed using analytic procedures used in grounded theory (Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

Result and Discussion

From the two standpoints of the study, several themes that describe the talent development experiences and talent development influences of the swimming athletes of the university emerged from the data analysis.

Under the talent development experiences, themes that were drawn from the experiences of the swimmers include the role of nature (genetics) that includes their physical characteristics; environmental opportunities that focus on the swimmer's geographical location to focus on swimming, personal sacrifices and emphasis on education; early successes in swimming which include lessons learned from competitions and the emotional development towards sport; and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers which pertain to the adversities during practice

and competitions, development of mindset and discipline to address adversities and increased motivation to succeed in swimming.

According to Simonton (2001), talent development in sports is a multifaceted and ever-evolving process that involves the interaction of performance, psycho-social, and educational factors. This process typically encompasses various stages within the sport, including initiation, talent development, talent retention, mastery, perfection/elite performance, as well as educational milestones such as elementary school, high school, and college/university/vocational education

Under the talent development influences, themes that were drawn from the experiences of the swimmers include the role of nurture (early influences) which include inspiration from family members; building positive influences like support from family members, inspiration from the coaches, love from teammates and logistic from school; enhancing positive influences which contains enhancing positive influences and enhancing coping and relief mechanisms; and nurturing positive influences like learning life skills for adaptation and cultivating positive relationships.

In relation to this, making informed decisions regarding pursuing an athletic career is crucial, as they directly impact the lives of athletes and their academic, sporting, familial, and peer support networks (Ryba et al., 2015). It is important to note that the literature on sports talent identification emphasizes the significance of key individuals and organizations in facilitating the holistic development of talented athletes. These influential actors play a vital role in promoting athlete well-being, supporting them during stressful situations across various life domains (e.g., training intensity, competition demands, injuries, social life constraints, and transitions to higher levels of competition and academia). That being said, by taking a comprehensive approach to talent development, athletes can maximize their potential while balancing their academic pursuits, personal relationships, and overall physical and mental well-being.

Overall, the winning qualities of the swimming athletes of the university are products of factors that influence them and the experiences that made them over the years since childhood. Their rich experiences which combined the role of nature (genetics), environmental opportunities, early successes in swimming, and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers and the combined force of influencing factors like the role of nurture (early influences), building enhancing and nurturing positive influences are influential in their talent development and growth as successful swimmers in the university. As such, it is essential to investigate the

combination of factors of experiences and influences when studying talent development that may create the winning qualities of student-athletes. From this combination of factors, one grounded theory was developed to explain how experiences and influences produce winning qualities in swimmers. This theory on the role of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence provides a bigger picture in understanding the role of experiences and influences in harnessing the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The swimming athletes of the university experiences of the swimmers develop their winning qualities in swimming due to their experiences that were brought by their nature (genetics), environmental opportunities, early successes in swimming, and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers. Also, building, enhancing, influencing, and nurturing positive influences in their life from childhood to the present help enhance their talent in swimming.

From these experiences and influences, theory showing a path to a successful college swimming career was concluded. This theory on the role of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence provides a bigger picture in understanding the role of experiences and influences in harnessing the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

This theory of experiences and influence toward swimming excellence may be used by the university especially the Office of the Sports and Development in designing a comprehensive talent development plan for future swimming athletes of the university and can even be applied to other competitive sports being participated in by the university. This will help maintain a reputable standing in the region as one of the powerhouses in swimming.

Also, the findings of the study may be used by the university in building a talent identification program that will help identify and scout prospective athletes at the elementary and secondary levels. These students who will be scouted based on the criteria mentioned in the theory of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence will be placed under the university's watch and be provided with ample support until the time they enter the university to become its athletes.

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